

Merocyanines and Azamerocyanines derived from 2-Hydroxy 1-Naphthaldehyde and 1-Nitroso 2-Naphthol

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Several merocyanines and azamerocyanines have been synthesised from 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol. The effect of replacement of = CH- by = N- in the methin chain has been studied.

In our present investigation a number of merocyanines and also azamerocyanines of general structure (I) have been prepared.

The merocyanines (I, X and Y = CH) were prepared by refluxing a mixture of 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde with different 2-methyl quaternary salts in alcohol and triethylamine. The azamerocyanines (I, X = N and Y = CH, nitrogen adjacent to the basic nucleus) were prepared by reaction of the same aldehyde (2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde) with 2-amino heterocyclic quaternary salts in the same solvent. The other type of azamerocyanines (I, X = CH, Y = N) (nitrogen adjacent to the acidic nucleus) were prepared by mixing a solution of 1-nitroso 2-naphthol with various 2-methyl quaternary salts in alcohol and triethylamine.

The absorption maxima of these dyes have been utilised for study of the effect of replacement of -CH = by -N =, in the chromophoric chain. It was observed that a hypsochromic shift occurred, when the -CH = group adjacent to the basic nuclei side was replaced by -N =, whereas a bathochromic shift resulted, when the -CH = group adjacent to the acidic nuclei side was replaced by = N- (Table I and II). These results are quite in accordance with Forster's Rule¹.

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1. F. F. Forster, *Z. Elektro Chem.*, 1939, **45**, 548.

TABLE I

Absorption data of merocyanines and azamerocyanines derived from 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde and 2-amino heterocyclic nuclei.

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Absorption maxima in $m\mu$		Observed shift	Expected shift
		X=Y=CH	X=N Y=CH		
Benzothiazole	2-Hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde	560	475	hypso	hypso
4-Phenyl thiazole	-do-	550	510	-do-	-do-

TABLE II

Absorption data of merocyanines and azamerocyanines derived from 1-nitroso 2-naphthol.

Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Absorption maxima in $m\mu$		Expected shift	Observed shift
		X=Y=CH	X=CH Y=N		
Benzothiazole	1-nitroso 2-naphthol	560	595	bathochromic	bathochromic
4-Phenyl thiazole	-do-	550	587	-do-	-do-
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	-do-	575	622	-do-	-do-
alpha-Naphththiazole	-do-	580	627	-do-	-do-
Quinaldine	-do-	600	640	-do-	-do-
Lepidine	-do-	640	—	—	—

EXPERIMENTAL

General procedure for the preparation of merocyanines: A mixture of 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde (0.01 *M*) and 2-methyl quaternary salt (0.01 *M*) were warmed in absolute alcohol (10 ml) for a minute. Triethylamine (1 to 2 drops) was then added and the mixture refluxed for a period of 45 min. to 1 hr. The product was isolated on cooling and was crystallised from alcohol.

The analytical data, m.p. etc., of the merocyanines prepared by the above procedure are given in Table III.

Preparation of azamerocyanines from 2-amino quaternary salts: The azamerocyanines were prepared by following the same procedure outlined for merocyanines by taking 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde (0.01 mole) and 2-amino quaternary salt (0.01 mole). The product which separated on cooling was washed with water and finally crystallised from alcohol.

The analytical data, m.p. etc., of the azamerocyanines are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Merocyanines and azamerocyanines derived from 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde

Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of X and Y	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{\max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
						Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Benzothiazole	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	=CH-CH=	76	202	560	75.60	75.68	4.62	4.73
4-Phenyl thiazole	-do-	=CH-CH=	70	222	550	76.89	76.96	4.90	4.95
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	-do-	=CH-CH=	74	195	575	80.09	80.18	5.00	5.01
alpha-Naphthathiazole	-do-	=CH-CH=	62	195	580	78.42	78.47	4.61	4.63
Quinaldine	-do-	=CH-CH=	52	170	600	86.18	82.24	5.59	5.68
Lepidine	-do-	=CH-CH=	58	221	640	86.17	86.24	5.60	5.68
Benzothiazole	-do-	=N-CH=	68	226	475	71.62	71.69	4.33	4.39
4-Phenyl thiazole	-do-	=N-CH=	62	230	510	73.19	73.24	4.63	4.68

General procedure for the preparation of azamerocyanines from 1-nitroso 2-naphthol: A mixture of 1-nitroso 2-naphthol (0.01 mole) and 2-methyl heterocyclic quaternary salt (0.01 mole) was stirred in acetic anhydride (10 ml) at room temperature till all the solids completely dissolved. Triethylamine (2 drops) was then added and the stirring was continued for an hour more. The dye separated during this period, was filtered, washed with water followed by rectified spirit and was finally crystallised from alcohol.

The analytical data, m.p. etc., of the related azamerocyanines are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Azamerocyanines derived from 1-nitroso 2-naphthol

Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{\max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Benzothiazole	60	250	595	71.60	71.69	4.38	4.40
4-Phenyl thiazole	48	150	587	73.11	73.13	4.63	4.65
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	56	216	622	77.12	77.14	4.75	4.76
Quinaldine	55	207	640	80.70	80.76	5.10	5.12
alpha-Naphthathiazole	73	223	627	74.96	75.00	4.29	4.34
beta-Naphthathiazole	67	173	636	74.90	75.00	4.31	4.34

The authors are grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for providing a fellowship to one of them (A.N.).